

Hemato - Psychological Designs in Decision Architecture

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Abstract

Managers are voyaging through 'busitagion', with interregnums shifting and sprouting uninterruptedly. This paper intends to explore hiatuses in managerial decisions as linked to 'busitagion' ('business' and 'contagion') scenario. Objective is to transport inventive reflection upon 'busitagion' that countenance 'disruptive mental' approximations'. Attempt is to address the interregnums problem based on empirical study (hematological investigation) that provides synthesis of psychological mechanisms and strategies. Authors have examined a recurring phenomenon i.e. disruption, plagued with 'orthodox managerial replicas' and 'disruptors' has submerged the environment. Hybrid 'disruptive mental' approximations' are emerging as alternative to model complex systems under uncertainty. Authors find that managers are at crossroads with neuroscience and business laying a linkage that seemed an abnormal approximation. Managers are endorsing an ever-increasing amount of multilevel research that integrate delineated research domains and offer new lenses for understanding managerial practice. This research is confronted with limitation of having based the study on hematological investigation. Future research should focus on finding larger samples and neuro - based approaches to instrument for to explore interregnums linked to 'busitagion' scenario. This research attempts to answer issues like; do managers have the information they need? Are managers using right models? Is there new analysis that could make managers effective? With focal point on 'busitagion'; how do managers choose among alternatives on what decide to take? What characteristics of alternatives would generate 'mental' approximations'? How 'variables' figured in brain would help managers develop judgement? The study is the first to use to use hematological investigation based analysis towards managerial theoretic reasoning and advances dialogues by providing perceptive specifics concerning how managers operate and behave towards a decision.

Key Words: Neuromanagement, 'Busitagion' Behaviours and Neuro 'Disruption' Management

Introduction

The biggest question in the latter part of the 20th Century and during the last two decades of the 21st Century has been; Are we, from the field of management science, arriving a ecosphere of neuro subtleties? Is neuromanagement, consecrated by neuroscience thrusting the spectrum of management into a vortex tube of neuro calculations and viewing it from a pair of neurobiology (biological mechanisms and functional circuits that process information and mediate behaviour) lenses? The voyagers fail to factor that right from the evolution of this universe, mankind has been in a constant dialogue with nature, environment, natural factors and spreading outdo embrace the essence of evolution, genetics, heredity and molecular operative milieus. This formed the foundation of Darwin's Model of 'Survivability' of 'Fittest'. This has a fine thread connation with the world of business administration, business management and business dynamics that revolve around the dynamics of 'judgement modeling' in a protoplasm of neuroecology. This calls for a peep into the archetype of cognitive construction of mental simulation in judgement construction.

Cerebrum receives indications, accentuate recognition and transduction to grow and die in stochastic milieus. Impression that judgements are taken through rational or logical thought process have been exposed to questioning by experiments that analyse estimation during judgement making. Rationality is unclear with stochastic complexity. Are business 'agent's being threatened by 'judgement alarm'? Is there a problem with judgement making? Reference is drawn to cerebrums that impact judgements, genes they activate to

differentiate based on multiple signals of origin, conditions that support or negate findings that aid understanding of how chromosomal configurations influence judgement making. Cerebrum - based judgement making can infer from noisy signals and anticipated state of business setting. Third, cells decide in presence of potentially competitive makers.

Judgements envelop business prospects. Research in judgment and judgement making has examined behavioural violations of rational judgement theory. Each business organisation is unique organically and landscape stimulates fresh queries, vigorous theoretical and conjectural practicalities, demanding approaches, challenging results, and audacious insinuations. Business organisations are at intersections with hematological science and business laying a conduit that seems an abnormal approximation with infinite 'scrolling' and 'interpolations' in 'disruptive hematological' guesstimates. Judgement 'impertinence' toward problem solving is used to portray business 'agent' as facing a set of alternative courses of action from which a judgement must be made. 'Assertiveness' assumes it as easy to come up with substitutions, but stimulating to choose among them is difficult to design a good alternative. Are business 'agent's being threatened by 'judgement alarm'? Business leaders assume that judgements they take are rational, optimal and based on best accessible data. They postulate that they are in total appreciation of judgemental behaviours. Such propositions are now scanned under lens of cellular and chromosomal prisms. Issues like how judgemental processes transgress in cerebrum pathways, how cerebrum considers sources of data and what intrinsic processes embody conflicting values have been explored to design 'rational' judgements. Inquiry is witnessing an ever-increasing amount of multilevel research in organisational studies that integrates delineated research domains and offers novel lens for understanding business practice. A recurring phenomenon i.e. disruption, global business arena is plagued with 'non - orthodox business replicas' and 'disruptors'.

Objective

Objective of this paper is to monitor philosophy of biology in behavioural models towards understanding neurobiological 'drivers' that underlie behaviour and judgement making by means of fundamental tools from economics, psychology, neuroscience, mathematics and statistics. Paper attempts propositions generated from theoretic 'mosaic' and presents directions advocated in 'Satpathy - Gankar' Hematological Calculation Model' via hematological (blood) analysis pathway. Considerations are based on critical analysis of relevant literature and hematological results obtained in an initial empirical study. These contribute in the direction of modeling cognitive construction of mental simulation.

Purpose

Investigation is countersigning an ever - increasing quantity of multilevel examination in judgement studies that assimilates delineated research provinces and offers innovative lens for appreciative judgemental run-through. There is a 'noise' for a tactic to make 'Hematisation' ('hematological or blood predilection' and 'judgement') a reality via avant-garde strategy. Paper attempts plans made from theoretical 'mosaic' and presents directions in 'Satpathy - Gankar' Calculation Model'. Purpose is to assess that hematological (blood) investigations have motivation on business 'agent's judgement. Focus is to replicate philosophy of neurobiology in research. Results demonstrate signs for unrehearsed counterfactual imitation.

Literature Framework

Neuro - Calibrations in business judgments has been a major incursion by business researchers in the 21st Century. Satpathy and Gankar, et.al. (2021; forthcoming) in a study on the Anthological Commentary on Haematological Guesstimates have coupled up few replicative studies towards preparing a mosaic of the mental calculations that go on in the brains at the time of perfecting a judgement. Satpathy and Gankar, et.al. (2021; forthcoming) in a study on the Hematological Signatures in Technopreneurial Judgement Corridors have outlined the complete blood count factors in a neuro - biochemistry treatment. Satpathy and Gankar, et.al.

(2021; forthcoming) in a study on the Neuro - Graduations in Business Judgments have calibrated the judgement matrices while being calculated by a business actor. Satpathy, J. (2020) has charted out the Neuro - Milieus in Technopreneurial Judgements by generating a protoplasmic setting in a judgement environment. Exploring the Noetic Alleyways: Choosing to Choose or Deciding to Decide, Satpathy, et. al. (2020) has portrayed the neural pathways undertaken by a manager in the journey of judgement making. In a surgical interpretation on Neuro - Couplings in Managerial Judgement, Satpathy and Gankar, et.al. (2020) have analysed the dynamics of neurotransmitters at synapses. A study on Neuro - Cursors in Managerial 'Judgement Mosaic' was undertaken by Satpathy and Gankar, et.al. (2020) wherein the authors have analysed the neuro cursors like fMRI, TMT, EEG, ECG etc. as determinants of judgement making. Satpathy (2020), with Prof Hejmadi, A. (2000) carried out an empirical study on Neuromanagement 'Judgement' as a precursor of judgement making. They also conducted a parallel study on Neuro - Smidgeons In Choosing To Decide and Skin Conductance in 'Smart' Managerial Judgement with Prof Gankar, S. (2020). Satpathy, J., Hejmadi, A. and Gankar, S. (2020) conducted replicative study on Ophthalmological Catalysts in Managerial Judgement to reveal that eyes are conductors of judgement making. This preceded a study on Visual Monikers in Managerial Judgements by Satpathy, J., Pati, P., Hejmadi, A., Gankar, S. and Malhotra, S. (2019). Do business judgements take a curve on the judgemental path (a graph summarizing his risk-taking attitude)? How do these integrate this risk - taking approach in judgement making? A paper was published by Satpathy, J., et. al. (2020) and Neena (2020) titled Neuro - Trajectories in Managerial Judgements. On this issue a parallel paper titled Random Reflections on Neuro judgements Dynamics (Satpathy, J. and Gera, S.; 2020) was submitted at the NeuroPsychoEconomics Conference Amsterdam, Netherlands with and Neuro - Smidgeons in Deciding to Decide Satpathy, J., Hejmadi, A. and Laza, S. (2020). A mathematical exposition under the title 'Computational 'Neuro - Trajectories' in Judgement Making' by Satpathy, J. and Mallik, B. (2020), lends credence to the issue in hand. A study on 'Genetic Underpinnings in Managerial Judgement' by Satpathy, J., Hejmadi, A., Singh, A. and Laza, S. (2020) explores the genetic traits associated with Neuro - Evidence Based Managerial Judgements.

Very few studies have been undertaken in the arena of judgement making and blood chemistry. In a meta-analysis of blood glucose effects on human judgement making, Literature claims that short-term changes in blood glucose influence predilections and may shake judgements. Orquin (2015) conducted a psychometric meta-analysis on the effect of blood glucose on judgement making. The analysis determines that blood glucose has domain-specific effects, swaying judgement making inversely. This study reflects the significance of having a unswerving blood indices level. In a parallel study on hematological judgment in managerial judgement, Satpathy and Mallik (2018) report role of 'hematological undercurrents' in managerial judgement making apparatus. Paper adds to different results, insights and knowledge by contrasting managerial judgement with hematology. Paper intends to comfort managers advance judgment in judgement skills.

The above literature reviews reflect cognitive construction of mental simulation through eye movement, sweat conductance and blood moniker dynamics. Very few studies have been undertaken in the arena of judgement making and blood chemistry except for Jacob L Orqun, Robert Kurzban, Jacob D Christensen, Carl Johan Lagerkvist, Satpathy, Mallik and Sayalee Gankar, to list a few as available in web engine search

Methodology

Methodology presents hematological (blood) investigations in judgement neuroscience. The complete blood count (CBC) methodology has been adopted. Paper attempts propositions generated from theoretic 'mosaic' and presents directions advocated in 'Satpathy - Gankar' hematological model' via hematological (blood) analysis pathway. Methodology includes collecting human blood samples from different age cohorts and judgement processes through neurobiological 'drivers' (hematological) that underlie behaviour exploring causal mechanisms of judgement routes by formal modeling and how the blood chemistry calculates with regard to questions in management and organisational comportment.

Findings and Results

Table: 1
Grouping of Respondents

Group 1:	Male subjects	(Aged : 25 - 40 years)	Total: 32	Total: 80
Group 2:	Male subjects	(Aged : 41 - 55 years)	Total: 29	
Group 3:	Male subjects	(Aged : 56 - 70 years)	Total: 19	
Group 4:	Female subjects	(Aged : 25 - 40 years)	Total: 31	
Group 5:	Female subjects	(Aged : 41 - 55 years)	Total: 30	
Group 6:	Female subjects	(Aged : 56 - 70 years)	Total: 09	
				Total: 70

Table: 2
Openness to Experience

Factor	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
Multifaceted	81 %	80 %	76 %	78 %	81 %	74 %
Resourceful	91 %	90 %	87 %	88 %	92 %	86 %
Deep	79 %	81 %	77 %	76 %	84 %	73 %
Reflective	76 %	86 %	84 %	74 %	85 %	88 %
Knowledgeable	76 %	79 %	72 %	79 %	77 %	77 %
Rational	61 %	68 %	64 %	64 %	65 %	65 %
Unproductive	12 %	10 %	09 %	19 %	08 %	08 %
Unchallenging	34 %	31 %	27 %	29 %	32 %	26 %

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
(Figures have been rounded off)

Table: 3
Decision to Join Business (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Factor	Male Agree	Male Disagree	Female Agree	Female Disagree
Training for business skills	94 %	06 %	91 %	09 %
Long run profit maximisation	78 %	22 %	59 %	41 %
Corporate social responsibility	12 %	78 %	18 %	82 %
Service to Society	16 %	84 %	37 %	63 %
Maximisation of sales	94 %	06 %	79 %	21 %
Improve market shares	91 %	09 %	66 %	34 %
Maximisation of shareholder value	87 %	13 %	53 %	47 %
Opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work.	79 %	21 %	55 %	45 %
I have reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard.	32 %	68 %	45 %	55 %
I expect to grow and my career path is clearly mapped out.	44 %	56 %	57 %	43 %
I come to work purely to get business done.	96 %	04 %	87 %	13 %
My loyalty is defined and I feel part of a team in business.	85 %	15 %	84 %	16 %
I feel business reciprocates effort put.	77 %	23 %	59 %	41 %
I am motivated to contribute 100% to	96 %	04 %	89 %	11 %

Business for future benefits.				
I will work for business indefinitely.	78 %	21 %	79 %	21 %
I work to achieve goals of business.	98 %	02 %	94 %	06 %
Being able to change things, I do not like about my business.	91 %	09 %	88 %	12 %
Having a say about the way I do things in my business.	95 %	05 %	91 %	09 %
Chance to learn new things in my work.	89 %	11 %	92 %	08 %
Chance to use my abilities within my business.	94 %	06 %	87 %	13 %
Chance of achieving something worthwhile.	93 %	07 %	91 %	09 %
I work for profit and expect to be paid for overtime.	99 %	01 %	97 %	03 %
Business is a high - concert occupation.	94 %	06 %	92 %	08%
Choice to remain involved (so) influential?	93 %	07 %	91 %	09 %
Business harnesses your potential.	79 %	21 %	76 %	24 %
‘Carrot and stick’ approach of motivating works in business.	57 %	43 %	68 %	32 %
Managers in business evaluate different practices of management.	69 %	31 %	71 %	29 %
Above factors, reflect desired values and virtues in business.	77 %	23 %	79 %	21 %
Above factors contribute towards better environment.	89 %	21 %	88 %	12 %

Table: 4

Overall Proficiency about Decision Making

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	51 %	49 %
41 - 55 Years	68 %	54 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	73 %

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

(Figures have been rounded off)

Table No: 5

Overall Person - Business Fit

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	71 %	69 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	84 %
56 - 70 Years	97 %	93 %

(Figures have been rounded off)

Table No. 6
Work - Personal Interface

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	71 %	69 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	84 %
56 - 70 Years	97 %	93 %

Table No. 7
Profit and Wages

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	74 %	59 %
41 - 55 Years	78 %	74 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	73 %

(Figures have been rounded off)

Table No. 8
Benefit Satisfaction Index

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	76 %	71 %
41 - 55 Years	81 %	79 %
56 - 70 Years	88 %	83 %

(Figures have been rounded off)

Table No. 9
Satisfaction Index

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	79 %	76 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	77 %
56 - 70 Years	89 %	87 %

Table No. 10
Deciding on Own

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	78 %	77 %
41 - 55 Years	86 %	75 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	85 %

(Figures have been rounded off)

Table No. 11**'Intelligence' Over Choices Selected'**

(N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

(Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	88 %	77 %
41 - 55 Years	89 %	78 %
56 - 70 Years	90 %	80 %

(Table - 12)**HAEMATOLOGICAL COUNTS**

MALE SUBJECTS (Aged : 25 - 40 Years)					
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)					
INDEX	RESULT			NORMAL VALUE	OBSN DURING STRESS
	NO STRESS	STRESSED	NO		
Blood Sugar Fasting	70 mg / dl	61 mg / dl		60 - 100	Drastic Drop
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	110 mg / dl	90 mg / dl		< 140	Drastic Drop
Blood Sugar Random	179 mg / dl	159 mg / dl		< 200	Drastic Drop
Urea	27 mg / dl	21 mg / dl		15 - 40	Drastic Drop
Creatine	0.6 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl		0.5 - 1.0	Minor Drop
Sodium	141 mEq / L	129 mEq / L		130 - 145	Drastic Drop
Potassium	3.9 mEq / L	3.2 mEq / L		3.5 - 5.0	Drastic Drop
Lipid T - Cholesterol	138 mg / dl	108 mg / dl		< 200	Drastic Drop
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	78 mg / dl	58 mg / dl		60 - 150	Drastic Drop
Low Density Lipo Protein	79 mg / dl	59 mg / dl		60 - 130	Drastic Drop
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	31 mg / dl	17 mg / dl		00 - 36	Drastic Drop
High Density Lipo Protein	56 mg / dl	36 mg / dl		40 - 60	Drastic Drop
S Bilirubin Total	0.9 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl		0.1 - 1.2	Drastic Drop
S Bilirubin Direct	0.12 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl		< 0.3	Drastic Drop
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl		0.1 - 1.0	Drastic Drop
Aspartate Trans Amines	24 IU / L	16 IU / L		15 - 40	Drastic Drop

Alanine Trans Amines	23 IU / L	16 IU / L	15 - 40	Drastic Drop
Creatine Phosphate K	21	4	M : 6 - 37	Drastic Drop
CPK - Muscular / Brain	14	12	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drop
T - Protein	6.3 g / dl	5.3 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drop
Albumin	3.9 g / dl	3.4 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drop
Globulin	1.9 g / dl	1.8 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drop

(Table - 13)

HAEMATOLOGICAL COUNTS

MALE SUBJECTS (Aged : 41 - 55 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN
	NO STRESS	STRESS		
Blood Sugar Fasting	71 mg / dl	70 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Post - Prandi	87 mg / dl	85 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Random	113 mg / dl	111 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Urea	19 mg / dl	14 mg / dl	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine	0.6 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.5 - 1.0	Drastic Drop
Sodium	141 mEq / L	131 mEq / L	130 - 145	Drastic Drop
Potassium	3.7 mEq / L	3.4 mEq / L	3.5 - 5.0	Minor Drop
Lipid T - Cholesterol	119 mg / dl	114 mg / dl	< 200	Drastic Drop
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	71 mg / dl	64 mg / dl	60 - 150	Drastic Drop
Low Density Lipo Protein	79 mg / dl	69 mg / dl	60 - 130	Drastic Drop
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	24 mg / dl	21 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drop
High Density Lipo Protein	48 mg / dl	45 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Total	0.8 mg / dl	0.5 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Direct	0.13 mg / dl	0.10 mg / dl	< 0.3	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.0	Drastic Drop
Aspartate Trans Amines	22 IU / L	19 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop

Alanine Trans Amines	19 IU / L	17 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine Phosphate K	21	18	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drop
CPK - Muscular / Brain	26	13	F : 5 - 27	Drastic Drop
T - Protein	6.7 g / dl	6.2 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drop
Albumin	3.6 g / dl	3.4 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drop
Globulin	1.2 g / dl	1.0 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drop

(Table –14)

HAEMATOLOGICAL COUNTS

MALE SUBJECTS (Aged : 56 - 70 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN DURING
	NO. STRESS	STRESSED		
Blood Sugar Fasting	74 mg / dl	73 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Post - Prandi	113 mg / dl	111 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Random	126 mg / dl	123 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Urea	25 mg / dl	22 mg / dl	15 – 40	Minor Drop
Creatine	0.9 mg / dl	0.7 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Minor Drop
Sodium	137 mEq / L	131 mEq / L	130 - 145	Minor Drop
Potassium	3.9 mEq / L	3.1 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Minor Drop
Lipid T - Cholesterol	124 mg / dl	120 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	76 mg / dl	71 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drop
Low Density Lipo Protein	79 mg / dl	73 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drop
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	14 mg / dl	12 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drop
High Density Lipo Protein	43 mg / dl	41 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Total	0.5 mg / dl	0.6 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Rise
S Bilirubin Direct	0.1 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	< 0.3	Minor Rise
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.5 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Minor Rise
Aspartate Trans Amines	21 IU / L	18 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop

Alanine Trans Amines	23 IU / L	21 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine Phosphate K	8	06	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drop
CPK - Muscular / Brain	11	08	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drop
T - Protein	6.4 g / dl	6.1 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drop
Albumin	3.7 g / dl	3.1 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drop
Globulin	1.7 g / dl	1.3 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drop

(Table – 15)

HAEMATOLOGICAL COUNTS

FEMALE SUBJECTS (Aged : 25 - 40 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN
	NO STRESS	STRESS		
Blood Sugar Fasting	76 mg / dl	56 mg / dl	60 - 100	Drastic Drop
Blood Sugar Post - Prandia	112 mg / dl	98 mg / dl	< 140	Drastic Drop
Blood Sugar Random	124 mg / dl	100 mg / dl	< 200	Drastic Drop
Urea	22 mg / dl	12 mg / dl	15 – 40	Drastic Drop
Creatine	0.4 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Drastic Drop
Sodium	121 mEq / L	101 mEq / L	130 - 145	Drastic Drop
Potassium	3.1 mEq / L	2.1 mEq / L	3.5 – 5.0	Drastic Drop
Lipid T - Cholesterol	102 mg / dl	92 mg / dl	< 200	Drastic Drop
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	62 mg / dl	61 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drop
Low Density Lipo Protein	76 mg / dl	72 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drop
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	12 mg / dl	11 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drop
High Density Lipo Protein	43 mg / dl	37 mg / dl	40 - 60	Drastic Drop
S Bilirubin Total	0.7 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Drastic Drop
S Bilirubin Direct	0.2 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	< 0.3	No Drop
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	No Drop

Aspartate Trans Amines	22 IU / L	18 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Alanine Trans Amines	21 IU / L	19 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine Phosphate K	7	4	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drop
CPK - Muscular / Brain	9	6	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drop
T - Protein	7 g / dl	6 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drop
Albumin	3.1 g / dl	30 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drop
Globulin	1.6 g / dl	1.4 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drop

(Table – 16)

HAEMATOLOGICAL COUNTS

FEMALE SUBJECTS (Aged : 41 - 55 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN
	NO STRESS	STRESS		
Blood Sugar Fasting	82 mg / dl	80 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	59 mg / dl	56 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Random	98 mg / dl	94 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Urea	16 mg / dl	11 mg / dl	15 – 40	Minor Drop
Creatine	0.6 mg / dl	0.4 mg / dl	0.5 – 1.0	Minor Drop
Sodium	121 mEq / l	110 mEq / l	130 - 145	Minor Drop
Potassium	3.2 mEq / l	2.2 mEq / l	3.5 – 5.0	Minor Drop
Lipid T - Cholesterol	79 mg / dl	72 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	71 mg / dl	68 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drop
Low Density Lipo Protein	65 mg / dl	62 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drop
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	12 mg / dl	09 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drop
High Density Lipo Protein	41 mg / dl	38 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Total	0.4 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Direct	0.1 mg / dl	0.1 mg / dl	< 0.3	No Change
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.4 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.1 – 1.0	Minor Drop
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	22 IU / L	19 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop

Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	21 IU / L	18 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine Phosphate K	7	5	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drop
CPK - Muscular / Brain	9	7	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drop
T - Protein	7 g / dl	5 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drop
Albumin	3.6 g / dl	3.2 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drop
Globulin	1.9 g / dl	1.7 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drop

(Table – 17)

HAEMATOLOGICAL COUNTS

FEMALE SUBJECTS (Aged : 56 - 70 Years)				
(ROUNDED - OFF AVERAGE RECORDINGS)				
INDEX	RESULT		NORMAL VALUE	OBSN DURING
	NO STRESS	STRESS		
Blood Sugar Fasting	47 mg / dl	46 mg / dl	60 - 100	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	78 mg / dl	76 mg / dl	< 140	Minor Drop
Blood Sugar Random	110 mg / dl	100 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Urea	14 mg / dl	13 mg / dl	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine	0.4 mg / dl	0.3 mg / dl	0.5 - 1.0	Minor Drop
Sodium	115 mEq / L	113 mEq / L	130 - 145	Minor Drop
Potassium	3.1 mEq / L	3.0 mEq / L	3.5 - 5.0	Minor Drop
Lipid T - Cholesterol	78 mg / dl	75 mg / dl	< 200	Minor Drop
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	48 mg / dl	45 mg / dl	60 - 150	Minor Drop
Low Density Lipo Protein	56 mg / dl	54 mg / dl	60 - 130	Minor Drop
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	24 mg / dl	22 mg / dl	00 - 36	Minor Drop
High Density Lipo Protein	39 mg / dl	37 mg / dl	40 - 60	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Total	0.3 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.2	Minor Drop
S Bilirubin Direct	0.1 mg / dl	0.1 mg / dl	< 0.3	No Change
S Bilirubin Indirect	0.3 mg / dl	0.2 mg / dl	0.1 - 1.0	Minor Drop
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	14 IU / L	12 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop

Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	13 IU / L	11 IU / L	15 - 40	Minor Drop
Creatine Phosphate K	05	04	M : 6 - 37	Minor Drop
CPK - Muscular / Brain	04	03	F : 5 - 27	Minor Drop
T - Protein	4.9 g / dl	4.7 g / dl	6 - 8	Minor Drop
Albumin	3.2 g / dl	3.0 g / dl	3.5 - 5.5	Minor Drop
Globulin	1.6 g / dl	1.4 g / dl	1.7 - 3.2	Minor Drop

(Table –18)

**AVERAGE OF DIFFERENT SITUATIONS
(SKIN CONDUCTANCE TEST)**

	Tasks	Conscious	Sense
Calibration	1.3057	1.5834	1.5365
Calibration	1.1112	1.1272	1.1373
Calibration	0.765 1	1.8456	1.0508
Calibration	1.0011	1.0757	1.0675
Calibration	0.7127	0.8803	0.7753
Calibration	1.101	1.1134	1.1104
Calibration	1.050	1.1186	1.0584
Calibration	0.6085	0.6435	0.6730
Calibration	1.0418	1.0574	1.0782
Calibration	1.2588	1.4431	1.4488
Calibration	0.7127	0.8803	0.7753

(Table –19)

TIME TO FIXATE

Time to First Fixation

Fixation_observation4.JPG_1_Mean	Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_1_Sum	Time to First
Fixation_observation4.JPG_2_N	Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_2_Mean	Time to First
Fixation_observation4.JPG_2_Sum	Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_3_N	Time to First
Fixation_observation4.JPG_3_Mean	Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_3_Sum	Time to First
Fixation_observation4.JPG_4_N	Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_4_Mean	Time to First
Fixation_observation4.JPG_4_Sum	Time to First Fixation_observation5.JPG_5_N	Time to First
Fixation_observation5.JPG_5_Mean	Time to First Fixation_observation5.JPG_5_Sum	Time to First
Fixation_observation6.JPG_6_N	Time to First Fixation_observation6.JPG_6_Mean	Time to First
Fixation_observation6.JPG_6_Sum	Time to First Fixation_observation6.JPG_7_N	Time to First
Fixation_observation6.JPG_7_Mean	Time to First Fixation_observation6.JPG_7_Sum	Time to First
Fixation_observation7.JPG_10_N	Time to First Fixation_observation7.JPG_10_Mean	Time to First
Fixation_observation7.JPG_10_Sum	Time to First Fixation_observation7.JPG_8_N	Time to First
Fixation_observation7.JPG_8_Mean	Time to First Fixation_observation7.JPG_8_Sum	Time to First
Fixation_observation7.JPG_9_N	Time to First Fixation_observation7.JPG_9_Mean	Time to First
Fixation_observation7.JPG_9_Sum	First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_1_N	First Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean	First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Sum	First Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_2_N	First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean	First Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Sum	First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_N	First Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean	First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Sum	First Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_4_N	First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean	First Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Sum	First Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_N	First Fixation
Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean	First Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Sum	First Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_6_N	First Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean	First Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Sum	First Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_N	First Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean	First Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Sum	First Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_10_N	First Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean	First Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Sum	First Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_N	First Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean	First Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Sum	First Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_9_N	First Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean	First Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Sum	Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_1_N	Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean	Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Sum	Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_2_N	Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean	Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Sum	Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_N	Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean	Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Sum	Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_4_N	Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean	Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Sum	Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_N	Fixation
Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean	Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Sum	Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_6_N	Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean	Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Sum	Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_N	Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean	Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Sum	Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_10_N	Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean	Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Sum	Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_N	Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean	Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Sum	Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_9_N	Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean	Fixation
Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Sum	Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_1_N	Total Fixation
Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean	Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Sum	Total Fixation

Duration_observation4.JPG_2_N Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Total Fixation
 Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Sum Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_N Total Fixation
 Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Sum Total Fixation
 Duration_observation4.JPG_4_N Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Total Fixation
 Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Sum Total Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_N Total Fixation
 Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Total Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Sum Total Fixation
 Duration_observation6.JPG_6_N Total Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Total Fixation
 Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Sum Total Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_N Total Fixation
 Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Total Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Sum Total Fixation
 Duration_observation7.JPG_10_N Total Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Total Fixation
 Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Sum Total Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_N Total Fixation
 Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean Total Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Sum Total Fixation
 Duration_observation7.JPG_9_N Total Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean Total Fixation
 Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Sum Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_1_N Fixation

Count_observation4.JPG_1_Mean Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_1_Sum Fixation
 Count_observation4.JPG_2_N Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Fixation
 Count_observation4.JPG_2_Sum Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_3_N Fixation
 Count_observation4.JPG_3_Mean Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_3_Sum Fixation
 Count_observation4.JPG_4_N Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Fixation
 Count_observation4.JPG_4_Sum Fixation Count_observation5.JPG_5_N Fixation
 Count_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Fixation Count_observation5.JPG_5_Sum Fixation
 Count_observation6.JPG_6_N Fixation Count_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Fixation
 Count_observation6.JPG_6_Sum Fixation Count_observation6.JPG_7_N Fixation
 Count_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Fixation Count_observation6.JPG_7_Sum Fixation
 Count_observation7.JPG_10_N Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Fixation
 Count_observation7.JPG_10_Sum Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_8_N Fixation
 Count_observation7.JPG_8_Mean Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_8_Sum Fixation
 Count_observation7.JPG_9_N Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_9_Mean Fixation
 Count_observation7.JPG_9_Sum Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_1_N Total Visit
 Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Sum Total Visit
 Duration_observation4.JPG_2_N Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Total Visit
 Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Sum Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_3_N Total Visit
 Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Sum Total Visit
 Duration_observation4.JPG_4_N Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Total Visit
 Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Sum Total Visit Duration_observation5.JPG_5_N Total Visit
 Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Sum Total Visit
 Duration_observation6.JPG_6_N Total Visit Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Total Visit
 Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Sum Total Visit Duration_observation6.JPG_7_N Total Visit
 Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Sum Total Visit
 Duration_observation7.JPG_10_N Total Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Total Visit
 Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Sum Total Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_8_N Total Visit
 Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Sum Total Visit
 Duration_observation7.JPG_9_N Total Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean Total Visit
 Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Sum Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_1_N Percentage
 Fixated_observation4.JPG_1_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_1_Sum Percentage
 Fixated_observation4.JPG_2_N Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Percentage
 Fixated_observation4.JPG_2_Sum Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_3_N Percentage

Fixated_observation4.JPG_3_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_3_Sum Percentage
 Fixated_observation4.JPG_4_N Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Percentage

Fixated_observation4.JPG_4_Sum Percentage Fixated_observation5.JPG_5_N Percentage
 Fixated_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation5.JPG_5_Sum Percentage
 Fixated_observation6.JPG_6_N Percentage Fixated_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Percentage
 Fixated_observation6.JPG_6_Sum Percentage Fixated_observation6.JPG_7_N Percentage
 Fixated_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation6.JPG_7_Sum Percentage
 Fixated_observation7.JPG_10_N Percentage Fixated_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Percentage
 Fixated_observation7.JPG_10_Sum Percentage Fixated_observation7.JPG_8_N Percentage
 Fixated_observation7.JPG_8_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation7.JPG_8_Sum Percentage
 Fixated_observation7.JPG_9_N Percentage Fixated_observation7.JPG_9_Mean Percentage
 Fixated_observation7.JPG_9_Sum

Rec 01	1	1.20	1.20	1	18.39	18.39	1	23.75	23.75	1	26.07	26.07	1	8.75		
		8.75	1	3.19	3.19	1	14.00	14.00	1	8.66	8.66	1	2.32	2.32	1	
		5.56	5.56	1	0.15	0.15	1	0.11	0.11	1	0.44	0.44	1	0.07	0.07	1
		0.17	0.17	1	0.39	0.39	1	0.17	0.17	1	0.17	0.17	1	0.24	0.24	1
		0.16	0.16	7	0.19	1.32	12	0.19	2.27	1	0.44	0.44	7	0.12	0.82	2
		0.12	0.25	10	0.19	1.94	1	0.17	0.17	7	0.15	1.06	3	0.16	0.47	4
		0.15	0.58	1	1.32	1.32	1	2.27	2.27	1	0.44	0.44	1	0.82	0.82	1
		0.25	0.25	1	1.94	1.94	1	0.17	0.17	1	1.06	1.06	1	0.47	0.47	1
		0.58	0.58	1	7.00	7.00	1	12.00	12.00	1	1.00	1.00	1	7.00	7.00	1
		2.00	2.00	1	10.00	10.00	1	1.00	1.00	1	7.00	7.00	1	3.00	3.00	1
		4.00	4.00	1	1.72	1.72	1	2.78	2.78	1	0.44	0.44	1	1.23	1.23	1
		0.25	0.25	1	2.28	2.28	1	0.17	0.17	1	1.73	1.73	1	0.94	0.94	1
		0.85	0.85	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
		100%		100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	
		100%		1	100%	100%							1	100%	100%	

Rec 02	1	3.97	3.97	1	29.23	29.23	1	35.48	35.48	1	39.96	39.96	1	14.63		
		14.63		1	12.08	12.08	1	45.81	45.81	1	22.38	22.38	1	3.13	3.13	1
		17.22		17.22	1	0.14	0.14	1	0.29	0.29	1	0.21	0.21	1	0.97	
		0.97	1	0.20	0.20	1	0.25	0.25	1	0.41	0.41	1	0.27	0.27	1	
		0.21	0.21	1	0.34	0.34	7	0.22	1.54	16	0.22	3.45	8	0.22	1.77	7
		0.35	2.44	13	0.24	3.07	15	0.28	4.22	9	0.23	2.04	15	0.19	2.91	8
		0.24	1.95	10	0.20	2.01	1	1.54	1.54	1	3.45	3.45	1	1.77	1.77	1
		2.44	2.44	1	3.07	3.07	1	4.22	4.22	1	2.04	2.04	1	2.91	2.91	1
		1.95	1.95	1	2.01	2.01	1	7.00	7.00	1	16.00	16.00	1	8.00	8.00	1
		7.00	7.00	1	13.00	13.00	1	15.00	15.00	1	9.00	9.00	1	15.00	15.00	1
		8.00	8.00	1	10.00	10.00	1	1.64	1.64	1	3.77	3.77	1	1.89	1.89	1
		2.55	2.55	1	3.34	3.34	1	4.56	4.56	1	2.70	2.70	1	3.77	3.77	1
		2.15	2.15	1	2.32	2.32	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
		100%		100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	
		100%		1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%				1	100%	100%	

Rec 03	1	3.18	3.18	1	31.36	31.36	1	49.27	49.27	1	53.08	53.08	1	18.93		
		18.93		1	8.97	8.97	1	42.40	42.40	1	20.88	20.88	1	3.93	3.93	1
		14.64		14.64	1	0.26	0.26	1	0.28	0.28	1	0.26	0.26	1	0.77	

0.771	0.35	0.35	1	0.25	0.25	1	0.31	0.31	1	0.33	0.33	1	
0.330.33	1	0.13	0.13	9	0.27	2.40	20	0.30	6.05	4	0.42	1.68	9
0.272.39	12	0.27	3.20	15	0.28	4.15	13	0.30	3.92	8	0.29	2.28	11
0.242.65	6	0.24	1.42	1	2.40	2.40	1	6.05	6.05	1	1.68	1.68	1
2.392.39	1	3.20	3.20	1	4.15	4.15	1	3.92	3.92	1	2.28	2.28	1
2.652.65	1	1.42	1.42	1	9.00	9.00	1	20.00	20.00	1	4.00	4.00	1
9.009.00	1	12.00	12.00	1	15.00	15.00	1	13.00	13.00	1	8.00	8.00	1
11.00	11.00	1	6.00	6.00	1	2.58	2.58	1	6.71	6.71	1	1.73	
1.731	2.73	2.73	1	3.68	3.68	1	4.70	4.70	1	4.15	4.15	1	
2.472.47	1	3.06	3.06	1	1.57	1.57	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1
100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	
100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%	1	100%	100%				

All Recordings	3	2.78	8.35	3	26.33	78.98	3	36.17	108.50	3	39.70	119.10	3
14.10	42.31	3	8.08	24.24	3	34.07	102.21	3	17.31	51.93	3	3.13	
9.383	12.48	37.43	3	0.18	0.55	3	0.23	0.68	3	0.30	0.91	3	
0.601.80	3	0.24	0.72	3	0.30	0.89	3	0.30	0.89	3	0.26	0.77	3
0.260.78	3	0.21	0.63	23	0.23	5.27	48	0.25	11.77	13	0.30	3.88	23
0.255.66	27	0.24	6.52	40	0.26	10.32	23	0.27	6.14	30	0.21	6.25	22
0.235.07	20	0.20	4.02	3	1.76	5.27	3	3.92	11.77	3	1.29	3.88	3
1.895.66	3	2.17	6.52	3	3.44	10.32	3	2.05	6.14	3	2.08	6.25	3
1.695.07	3	1.34	4.02	3	7.67	23.00	3	16.00	48.00	3	4.33	13.00	3
7.6723.00	3	9.00	27.00	3	13.33	40.00	3	7.67	23.00	3	10.00	30.00	3
7.3322.00	3	6.67	20.00	3	1.98	5.94	3	4.42	13.27	3	1.36	4.07	3
2.176.52	3	2.42	7.27	3	3.84	11.53	3	2.34	7.02	3	2.66	7.97	3
2.056.15	3	1.58	4.74	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3
100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	
300%	3	100%	300%	3	100%	300%							

Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_1_Mean **Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_2_Mean**
Time to First Fixation_observation4.JPG_3_Mean **Time to First**
Fixation_observation4.JPG_4_Mean **Time to First Fixation_observation5.JPG_5_Mean** **Time to**
First Fixation_observation6.JPG_6_Mean **Time to First Fixation_observation6.JPG_7_Mean** **Time to**
First Fixation_observation7.JPG_10_Mean **Time to First Fixation_observation7.JPG_8_Mean**
Time to First Fixation_observation7.JPG_9_Mean **First Fixation**
Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean **First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean** **First**
Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean **First Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean**
First Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean **First Fixation**
Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean **First Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean** **First**
Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean **First Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean**
First Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean **Fixation**
Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean **Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean** **Fixation**
Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean **Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean** **Fixation**
Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean **Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean** **Fixation**
Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean **Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean** **Fixation**
Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean **Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean** **Total Fixation**
Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean **Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean** **Total**
Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean **Total Fixation Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean**

Total Fixation Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Total Fixation
Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Total Fixation Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Total
Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Total Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean
Total Fixation Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_1_Mean
Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_3_Mean
Fixation Count_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Fixation Count_observation5.JPG_5_Mean
Fixation Count_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Fixation Count_observation6.JPG_7_Mean
Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_8_Mean
Fixation Count_observation7.JPG_9_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_1_Mean
Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Total Visit
Duration_observation4.JPG_3_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Total Visit
Duration_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Total Visit
Duration_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Total
Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_8_Mean Total Visit Duration_observation7.JPG_9_Mean
Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_1_Mean Percentage
Fixated_observation4.JPG_2_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation4.JPG_3_Mean Percentage
Fixated_observation4.JPG_4_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation5.JPG_5_Mean Percentage
Fixated_observation6.JPG_6_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation6.JPG_7_Mean Percentage
Fixated_observation7.JPG_10_Mean Percentage Fixated_observation7.JPG_8_Mean Percentage
Fixated_observation7.JPG_9_Mean

Rec 01	1.20	18.39	23.75	26.07	8.75	3.19	14.00	8.66	2.32	5.56	0.15	0.11	0.44	0.07
	0.17	0.39	0.17	0.17	0.24	0.16	0.19	0.19	0.44	0.12	0.12	0.19	0.17	0.15
	0.16	0.15	1.32	2.27	0.44	0.82	0.25	1.94	0.17	1.06	0.47	0.58	7.00	12.00
	1.00	7.00	2.00	10.00	1.00	7.00	3.00	4.00	1.72	2.78	0.44	1.23	0.25	2.28
	0.17	1.73	0.94	0.85	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Rec 02	3.97	29.23	35.48	39.96	14.63	12.08	45.81	22.38	3.13	17.22	0.14	0.29	0.21	0.97
	0.20	0.25	0.41	0.27	0.21	0.34	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.35	0.24	0.28	0.23	0.19
	0.24	0.20	1.54	3.45	1.77	2.44	3.07	4.22	2.04	2.91	1.95	2.01	7.00	16.00
	8.00	7.00	13.00	15.00	9.00	15.00	8.00	10.00	1.64	3.77	1.89	2.55	3.34	4.56
	2.70	3.77	2.15	2.32	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Rec 03	3.18	31.36	49.27	53.08	18.93	8.97	42.40	20.88	3.93	14.64	0.26	0.28	0.26	0.77
	0.35	0.25	0.31	0.33	0.33	0.13	0.27	0.30	0.42	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.30	0.29
	0.24	0.24	2.40	6.05	1.68	2.39	3.20	4.15	3.92	2.28	2.65	1.42	9.00	20.00
	4.00	9.00	12.00	15.00	13.00	8.00	11.00	6.00	2.58	6.71	1.73	2.73	3.68	4.70
	4.15	2.47	3.06	1.57	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

ALL RECORDINGS

26.33	36.17	39.70	14.10	8.08	34.07	17.31	3.13	12.48	0.18	0.23	0.30	0.60	0.24
	0.30	0.30	0.26	0.26	0.21	0.23	0.25	0.30	0.25	0.24	0.26	0.27	0.21
	0.20	1.76	3.92	1.29	1.89	2.17	3.44	2.05	2.08	1.69	1.34	7.67	16.00
	7.67	9.00	13.33	7.67	10.00	7.33	6.67	1.98	4.42	1.36	2.17	2.42	3.84
	2.66	2.05	1.58	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

100% 100% 100% 100%

T-Test

GET

FILE='C:\Users\Ritika.DESKTOP-730O9R4\Desktop\phd data final\JS SIR DATA.sa v'.

DATASET NAME DataSet1 WINDOW=FRONT. T-TEST GROUPS=Gender(1 2)

/MISSING=ANALYSIS

/VARIABLES=BSF BSP BSR UREA CREATINE SODIUM POTASSIUM LTC LTG LDLP VLDLP HD LP SBT SBD SBI AST ALT CPK CPKMB GGT TP ALBUMIN GLOBULIN AGRATIO

/CRITERIA=CI(.95).

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Group Statistics

	Gen	N	Mean	Std. Deviat	Std. Error Me
Blood Sugar Fasting	Male	6	61.67	11.112	4.536
	Fem	6	60.00	15.218	6.213
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	Male	6	120.00	26.06	10.64
	Female	6	119.67	45.994	18.77
Blood Sugar Random	Male	6	171.00	41.536	16.957
	Fem	6	152.33	46.449	18.963
Urea	Male	6	32.67	11.130	4.544
	Fem	6	32.33	17.317	7.069
Creatine	Male	6	.9833	.63061	.25744
	Fem	6	.9667	.55737	.22755
Sodium	Male	6	143.50	4.461	1.821
	Fem	6	134.00	16.721	6.826
Potassium	Male	6	4.3667	1.15007	.46952
	Fem	6	4.1333	1.09666	.44771
Lipid T - Cholesterol	Male	6	162.83	63.307	25.845
	Fem	6	134.67	53.865	21.990
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	Male	6	107.83	39.148	15.982
	Fem	6	110.33	55.745	22.758
Low Density Lipo Protein	Male	6	99.83	44.065	17.990
	Fem	6	115.67	55.500	22.658
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	Male	6	32.67	12.024	4.910
	Female	6	34.33	26.211	10.701
High Density Lipo Protein	Male	6	57.00	9.839	4.017
	Fem	6	51.00	12.458	5.086

	Gen	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Me
S Bilirubin Total	Male	6	1.2000	.57619	.23523
	Female	6	.9667	.57850	.23617
S Bilirubin Direct	Male	6	.3333	.26583	.10853
	Female	6	.8167	1.18392	.48333
S Bilirubin Indirect	Male	6	.9000	.54772	.22361
	Female	6	1.0333	.80166	.32728
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	Male	6	32.33	11.039	4.507
	Female	6	31.00	13.130	5.360
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	Male	6	33.33	13.049	5.327
	Female	6	30.00	13.130	5.360
Creatine Phosphate K	Male	6	26.67	12.372	5.051
	Female	6	26.33	21.933	8.954
CPK - Muscular / Brain	Male	6	22.50	12.818	5.233
	Female	6	18.83	12.891	5.263
GGT	Male	6	18.00	4.648	1.897
	Female	6	15.67	5.680	2.319
T - Protein	Male	6	7.0000	.77460	.31623
	Female	6	7.6333	1.65005	.67363
Albumin	Male	6	4.7333	1.10393	.45068
	Female	6	4.3000	1.12071	.45753
Globulin	Male	6	2.6000	1.14193	.46619
	Female	6	2.7000	1.10635	.45166
A : G Ratio	Male	6	.00	.000 ^a	.000
	Female	6	.00	.000 ^a	.000

a. t cannot be computed because the standard deviations of both groups are 0.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Sig.	t	
Blood Sugar Fasting	Equal variances assumed	1.003	.340	.217	
	Equal variances not assumed				
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	Equal variances assumed	2.258	.164	.015	
	Equal variances not assumed				
Blood Sugar Random	Equal variances assumed	.839	.381	.015	.734
	Equal variances not assumed				
Urea	Equal variances assumed	3.821	.079	.040	.734
	Equal variances not assumed				
Creatine	Equal variances assumed	.008	.931	.049	.040
	Equal variances not assumed				
Sodium	Equal variances assumed	63.048	.000	1.345	.049
	Equal variances not assumed				
Potassium	Equal variances assumed	.052	.825	.360	1.345
	Equal variances not assumed				
Lipid T - Cholesterol	Equal variances assumed	.924	.359	.830	.360
	Equal variances not assumed				
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	Equal variances assumed	4.932	.051	-.547	.830
	Equal variances not assumed				
Low Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	2.640	.135	-.547	-.090
	Equal variances not assumed				

t-test for Equality of Means

		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Blood Sugar Fasting	Equal variances assumed	10	.833	1.667
	Equal variances not assumed	9.151	.833	1.667
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	Equal variances assumed	10	.988	.333
	Equal variances not assumed	7.911	.988	.333
Blood Sugar Random	Equal variances assumed	10	.480	18.667
	Equal variances not assumed	9.878	.480	18.667
Urea	Equal variances assumed	10	.969	.333
	Equal variances not assumed	8.529	.969	.333
Creatine	Equal variances assumed	10	.962	.01667
	Equal variances not assumed	9.851	.962	.01667
Sodium	Equal variances assumed	10	.208	9.500
	Equal variances not assumed	5.708	.230	9.500
Potassium	Equal variances assumed	10	.727	.23333
	Equal variances not assumed	9.977	.727	.23333
Lipid T - Cholesterol	Equal variances assumed	10	.426	28.167
	Equal variances not assumed	9.750	.426	28.167
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	Equal variances assumed	10	.930	-2.500
	Equal variances not assumed	8.967	.930	-2.500
Low Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	10	.596	-15.833
	Equal variances not assumed	9.511	.597	-15.833

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		95% Confidence Interval of the		
		-Std. Difference	Lower	Upper
Blood Sugar Fasting	Equal variances assumed	7.693	-15.474	18.807
	Equal variances not assumed	7.693	-15.692	19.025
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	Equal variances assumed	21.582	-47.754	-48.421
	Equal variances not assumed	21.582	-49.533	50.199
Blood Sugar Random	Equal variances assumed	25.	-38.0	75.347
	Equal variances not assumed	25.	-38.1	75.442
Urea	Equal variances assumed	8.	-18.5	19.058
	Equal variances not assumed	8.	-18.8	19.505
Creatine	Equal variances assumed	.34	-.748	.78224
	Equal variances not assumed	.34	-.750	.78381
Sodium	Equal variances assumed	7.	-6.2	25.242
	Equal variances not assumed	7.	-8.0	27.004
Potassium	Equal variances assumed	.64	-1.212	1.67886
	Equal variances not assumed	.64	-1.212	1.67930
Lipid T - Cholesterol	Equal variances assumed	33.	-47.4	103.777
	Equal variances not assumed	33.	-47.5	104.041
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	Equal variances assumed	27.	-64.4	59.462
	Equal variances not assumed	27.	-65.4	60.444
Low Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	28.	-80.2	48.629
	Equal variances not assumed	28.	-80.5	49.081

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of
		F	Sig.	t
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	1.485	.251	-.142
	Equal variances not assumed			-.142
High Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	.431	.521	.926
	Equal variances not assumed			.926
S Bilirubin Total	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	.700
	Equal variances not assumed			.700
S Bilirubin Direct	Equal variances assumed			-.976
	Equal variances not assumed	4.721	.032	-.976
S Bilirubin Indirect	Equal variances assumed			-.336
	Equal variances not assumed	1.521	.215	-.336
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	Equal variances assumed	1.521	.215	.190
	Equal variances not assumed			.190
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	.441
	Equal variances not assumed			.441
Creatine Phosphate K	Equal variances assumed	17.578	.002	.032
	Equal variances not assumed			.032
CPK - Muscular / Brain	Equal variances assumed	.261	.621	.494
	Equal variances not assumed			.494
GGT	Equal variances assumed	.792	.379	.779
	Equal variances not assumed			.779

t-test for Equality of Means

		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	10	.890	-1.667
	Equal variances not assumed	7.016	.891	-1.667
High Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	10	.376	6.000
	Equal variances not assumed	9.490	.377	6.000
S Bilirubin Total	Equal variances assumed	10	.500	.23333
	Equal variances not assumed	10.000	.500	.23333
S Bilirubin Direct	Equal variances assumed	10	.352	-.48333
	Equal variances not assumed	5.503	.370	-.48333
S Bilirubin Indirect	Equal variances assumed	10	.744	-.13333
	Equal variances not assumed	8.833	.744	-.13333
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	Equal variances assumed	10	.853	1.333
	Equal variances not assumed	9.714	.853	1.333
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	Equal variances assumed	10	.669	3.333
	Equal variances not assumed	10.000	.669	3.333
Creatine Phosphate K	Equal variances assumed	10	.975	.333
	Equal variances not assumed	7.889	.975	.333
CPK - Muscular / Brain	Equal variances assumed	10	.632	3.667
	Equal variances not assumed	10.000	.632	3.667
GGT	Equal variances assumed	10	.454	2.333
	Equal variances not assumed	9.627	.455	2.333

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		95% Confidence Interval of the		
		Std. Difference	Lower	Upper
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	11.774	-27.900	24.567
	Equal variances not assumed	11.774	-29.494	26.161
High Density Lipo Protein	Equal variances assumed	6.	-8.440	20.440
	Equal variances not assumed	6.	-8.546	20.546
S Bilirubin Total	Equal variances assumed	.33	-.50938	.97605
	Equal variances not assumed	.33	-.50938	.97605
S Bilirubin Direct	Equal variances assumed	.33	-.50938	.97605
	Equal variances not assumed	.49	-1.58708	.62041
S Bilirubin Indirect	Equal variances assumed	.49	-1.72250	.75583
	Equal variances not assumed	.39	-1.01651	.74984
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	Equal variances assumed	.39	-1.03258	.76592
	Equal variances not assumed	7.	-14.271	16.937
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	Equal variances assumed	7.	-14.333	17.000
	Equal variances not assumed	7.	-13.505	20.172
Creatine Phosphate K	Equal variances assumed	7.	-13.505	20.172
	Equal variances not assumed	10.2	-22.5	23.240
CPK - Muscular / Brain	Equal variances assumed	10.2	-23.4	24.098
	Equal variances not assumed	7.4	-12.80	20.203
GGT	Equal variances assumed	7.4	-12.80	20.203
	Equal variances not assumed	2.9	-4.3	9.009
		2.9	-4.3	9.045

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of
		F	Sig.	t
T - Protein	Equal variances assumed	4.386	.063	.851
	Equal variances not assumed			-.851
Albumin	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	.675
	Equal variances not assumed			.675
Globulin	Equal variances assumed	.000	1.000	-.154
	Equal variances not assumed			-.154

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
T - Protein	Equal variances assumed	10	.445	
	Equal variances not assumed	7.102	.422	-.63333
Albumin	Equal variances assumed	10	.515	.43333
	Equal variances not assumed	9.998	.515	.43333
Globulin	Equal variances assumed	10	.881	-.10000
	Equal variances not assumed	9.990	.881	-.10000

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			Lower	Upper
T - Protein	Equal variances assumed	.74416	-2.29143	1.02476
	Equal variances not assumed	.74416	-2.38790	1.12124
Albumin	Equal variances assumed	.64222	-.99762	1.86429
	Equal variances not assumed	.64222	-.99766	1.86433
Globulin	Equal variances assumed	.64910	-1.54629	1.34629
	Equal variances not assumed	.64910	-1.54649	1.34649

ONEWAY BSF BSP BSR UREA CREATINE SODIUM POTASSIUM LTC LTG LDLP VLDLP HDLP SBT SBD SBI AST ALT CPK CPKMB GGT TP ALBUMIN GLOBULIN AGRATIO BY Age

/MISSING ANALYSIS.

Oneway

[DataSet1] C:\Users\Ritika.DESKTOP-730O9R4\Desktop\phd data final\JS SIR DATA

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		Sum of Squa	df	Mean Squ	F
Blood Sugar Fasting	Between Groups	61.800	2	30.900	.163
	Within Groups	1721.867	9	191.319	
	Total	1783.667	11		
Blood Sugar Post - Prandial	Between Groups	1728.200	2	864.100	.633
	Within Groups	12245.467	9	1360.607	
	Total	13973.667	11		
Blood Sugar Random	Between Groups	3452.200	2	1726.100	.911
	Within Groups	17006.467	9	1889.607	
	Total	20458.667	11		
Urea	Between Groups	178.333	2	89.167	.414
	Within Groups	1940.667	9	215.630	
	Total	2119.000	11		
Creatine	Between Groups	.196	2	.098	.263
	Within Groups	3.347	9	.372	
	Total	3.543	11		
Sodium	Between Groups	359.583	2	179.792	1.149
	Within Groups	1408.667	9	156.519	
	Total	1768.250	11		
Potassium	Between Groups	.305	2	.153	.110
	Within Groups	12.485	9	1.387	
	Total	12.790	11		
Lipid T - Cholesterol	Between Groups	735.450	2	367.725	.091
	Within Groups	36190.800	9	4021.200	
	Total	36926.250	11		
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	Between Groups	2182.250	2	1091.125	.467
	Within Groups	21036.667	9	2337.407	
	Total	23218.917	11		
Low Density Lipo Protein	Between Groups	369.450	2	184.725	.063
	Within Groups	25492.800	9	2832.533	
	Total	25862.250	11		
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	Between Groups	1232.133	2	616.067	1.883
	Within Groups	2934.867	9	326.096	
	Total	4167.000	11		
High Density Lipo Protein	Between Groups	196.800	2	98.400	.750
	Within Groups	1171.200	9	130.133	
	Total	1368.000	11		

		Sig.
Blood Sugar Fasting	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.853
Blood Sugar Post - Prandia	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.552
Blood Sugar Random	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.435
Urea	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.673
Creatine	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.774
Sodium	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.359
Potassium	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.897
Lipid T - Cholesterol	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.913
Lipid Tri - Glyceride	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.641
Low Density Lipo Protein	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.937
Very Low Density Lipo Protein	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.207
High Density Lipo Protein	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.497

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	1.281
S Bilirubin Total	Between Groups	2	2.722	11	.247		
	Within Groups Total	9	3.497	2	.320		
S Bilirubin Direct	Between Groups	2	.641	9	.825		
	Within Groups Total	11	7.422	2	.024		
S Bilirubin Indirect	Between Groups	2	8.063	9	.524		
	Within Groups Total	11	4.719	2	.046		
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	Between Groups	2	128.800	9	64.400	.430	
	Within Groups Total	11	1347.867	2	149.763		
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	Between Groups	2	97.800	9	48.900	.267	
	Within Groups Total	11	1648.867	2	183.207		
Creatine Phosphate K	Between Groups	2	325.800	9	162.900	.000	
	Within Groups Total	11	2845.200	2	316.133		
CPK - Muscular / Brain	Between Groups	2	3171.000	9	104.933		
	Within Groups Total	11	209.867	2	164.756		
GGT	Between Groups	2	1482.800	9	164.756		
	Within Groups Total	11	1692.667	2	4.600		
T - Protein	Between Groups	2	9.200	9	30.719		
	Within Groups Total	11	276.467	2	.181		
Albumin	Between Groups	2	285.667	9	1.939		
	Within Groups Total	11	.362	2	.000		
Globulin	Between Groups	2	17.455	9	1.939		
	Within Groups Total	11	17.817	2	.601		
A : G Ratio	Between Groups	2	1.202	9	1.304		
	Within Groups Total	11	11.735	2	.481		
	Between Groups	2	12.937	9	1.301		
	Within Groups Total	11	.961	2	.000		
	Between Groups	2	11.709	9	1.301		
	Within Groups Total	11	12.670	2	.000		
	Between Groups	2	.000	9	.000		
	Within Groups Total	11	.000	2	.000		

11

.515

.637

.150

.093

.461

.369

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		Sig.
S Bilirubin Total	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.324
S Bilirubin Direct	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.689
S Bilirubin Indirect	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.955
Aspartate Trans Amines (AST)	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.663
Alanine Trans Amines (ALT)	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.772
Creatine Phosphate K	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.614
CPK - Muscular / Brain	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.551
GGT	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.863
T - Protein	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.912
Albumin	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.645
Globulin	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.701
A : G Ratio	Between Groups Within Groups Total	.

Observations

- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Blood Sugar Fasting readings are observed as 'NORMAL (ABNORMAL)'.

- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Blood Sugar Post – Prandial readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Blood Sugar Random readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Urea readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Creatine readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Sodium readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Potassium readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when S Bilirubin Direct readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when S Bilirubin Indirect readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Aspartate Trans Amines (AST) readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Alanine Trans Amines (ALT) readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Lipid T – Cholesterol readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Lipid Tri – Glyceride readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Low Density Lipo Protein readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Very Low Density Lipo Protein readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when High Density Lipo Protein readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when S Bilirubin Total readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Creatine Phosphate K readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when CPK - Muscular / Brain readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when GGT readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when T - Protein readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Albumin readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when Globulin readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.
- Decision making potential is good (Bad) when A: G Ratio readings are observed as ‘NORMAL (ABNORMAL)’.

Conclusion

The only conclusion drawn is that when the blood parameters are 'NORMAL (ABNORMAL)', then the decision making potential is good (Bad).

Major finding is that business 'agent' attempts to decide and evaluates prospective judgement using neuro - hematological (blood) medium. Paper discusses new findings to understand neuro - hematological (blood) chromosomal design and offers to answer issues in data - driven leadership judgement-making dynamics.

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